

PROTOTYPE OF PRIMARY PROCESSING TOOLS AND SYSTEMS AND PROTOCOL FOR IMPLEMENTATION

D5.10

Website	foodland-africa.eu
Twitter	@FoodLANDafrica
Facebook	FoodLANDafrica
LinkedIn	foodland-africa

FOODLAND has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (GA No 862802).

The views and opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Deliverable information	
Deliverable no.:	D5.10
Work package no.:	WP5
Document version:	V1
Document Preparation Date:	30.12.2024
Responsibility:	MAK

Project information	
Project acronym and name:	FoodLAND
EC Grant Agreement no.:	862802
Project coordinator:	UNIBO
Project start date:	01.09.2020
Duration:	54 months

Document Information & Version Management			
Document title:	Prototype of primary processing tools and systems and protocol for implementation		
Document type:	Demonstrator		
Main author(s):	MAK, INAT, SUA		
Contributor(s):	NARO, UoN, UoM, ISACM		
Reviewed by:	MAK		
Approved by:	UNIBO		
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
V1	30.12.2024		

Short Description
<p>This deliverable describes different primary food processing prototypes developed by the project (drying, milling, fish processing systems), highlighting the prototype objectives, development activities, summary of results, prototype testing and validation, and arrangements for implementation and management of the project prototypes. This deliverable contains information that informs generation of protocol guideline (D4.9), practice abstracts (D6.5) and training materials (D5.1).</p>

Dissemination level	
PU	Public

FOODLAND has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (GA No 862802).

The views and opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. The publication reflects the author's views. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

FOODLAND has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (GA No 862802).

The views and opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Table of Contents

1.	General introduction.....	6
2.	Osmotic dehydration and solar drying prototypes	8
2.1	Osmotic dehydration and solar drying of fruits and vegetables (Jendouba, TN).....	8
2.1.1	Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	8
2.1.2	Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	8
2.1.3	Summary of the outputs	9
2.1.4	Summary of the outcomes	11
2.1.5	Summary of the impacts	11
2.1.6	Protocol for prototype implementation.....	12
2.1.7	Conclusions	16
2.2	Tomato tree drying using Innovative Hybrid Solar Drier (Kitui, KE)	17
2.2.1	Prototype motivations and objectives	17
2.2.2	Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	18
2.2.3	Summary of the outputs	19
2.2.4	Summary of the outcomes	25
2.2.5	Summary of the impacts	26
2.2.6	Protocol for prototype implementation.....	26
2.2.7	Conclusions	29
2.3	Eggplant drying (Nakaseke, UG)	30
2.3.1	Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	30
2.3.2	Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	30
2.3.3	Summary of the outputs	31
2.3.4	Summary of the outcomes	31

2.3.5 Summary of the impacts	32
2.3.6 Protocol for prototype implementation.....	32
2.3.7 Conclusions	35
2.4 Fish solar drying (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)	36
2.4.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	36
2.4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	36
2.4.3 Summary of the outputs	37
2.4.4 Summary of the outcomes	38
2.4.5 Summary of the impacts	38
2.4.6 Protocol for prototype implementation.....	38
2.4.7 Conclusions	41
2.5 Vegetables drying (Kilombero, TZ).....	42
2.5.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	42
2.5.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	42
2.5.3 Summary of the outputs	44
2.5.4 Summary of the outcomes	44
2.5.5 Summary of the impacts	45
2.5.6 Protocol for prototype implementation.....	45
2.5.7 Conclusions	48
3. Milling	49
3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	49
3.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	50
3.3 Summary of the outputs	55
3.3.1 Results and achievements.....	55
3.3.2 Relevant productions.....	56
3.4 Summary of the outcomes	57
3.5 Summary of the impacts	58
3.6 Protocol for prototype implementation	60

3.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture	60
3.6.3 Implementation.....	61
3.6.4 Management	63
3.7 Conclusions.....	63
4. Fish smoking (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)	63
4.1 Protocol background, motivation and objectives.....	63
4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	64
4.3 Summary of the outputs	65
4.3.1 Results and achievements.....	65
4.3.2 Relevant production	66
4.4 Summary of the outcomes	66
4.5 Summary of the impacts.....	66
4.6 Protocol for prototype implementation	67
4.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype	67
4.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture	67
4.6.3 Implementation.....	67
4.6.4 Management	68
4.7 Conclusions.....	69
5. Fish fermentation (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)	69
5.1 Protocol background, motivation and objectives.....	69
4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating	70
5.3 Summary of the outputs	71
5.3.1 Results and achievements.....	71
5.3.2 Relevant production	72
5.4 Summary of the outcomes	72
5.5 Summary of the impacts.....	72
5.6 Protocol for prototype implementation	72
5.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype	72

5.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture	73
5.6.3 Implementation.....	73
5.6.4 Management	74
5.7 Conclusions.....	74
6. General conclusion.....	75

Abbreviations and glossary

Abbreviation/specialist term	Explanation
AOAC	Association of Analytical Chemists
GDA	Agricultural development group
GHPs	Good handling practices
HACCP	Hazard analysis and critical control points
ISD	Innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer
KE	Kenya
KEPC	Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Ltd.
LAB	Lactic acid bacteria
SOPs	Standard operating procedures
ST	Solar tunnel
TN	Tunisia
TZ	Tanzania
UG	Uganda

1. General introduction

The FoodLAND project identified a variety of foods to promote for improved nutrition performance. Utilisation of these foods requires availability of appropriate technologies, covering the entire value chain. Primary processing covers the preliminary processing steps including those like milling that facilitate conversion of agricultural commodities into food products and some like drying and smoking that make foods more stable. This deliverable contains descriptions of different primary processing prototypes developed and/ or applied to selected foods. A list of the primary processing prototypes contained in this deliverable, with the corresponding raw materials and target food hubs are provided in Table 1 below. The deliverable covers justification and objectives of each prototype, outline of prototype development, testing and validation activities undertaken, key results, outcomes and impact (including key performance indicators), as well as protocol implementation plans. The descriptions are designed to portray the impact pathway, reflecting project inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impact (Figure 1). Effort is made to capture impact on targeted population, i.e. food operators and consumers with respect to aspects directly addressed by project interventions (primary impact), as well as in cross-cutting aspects such as the environment and policy (secondary impact).

Table 1: Primary processing technologies applied to different food commodities

Applied primary processing	Food Hub	Food commodities
Osmotic dehydration solar drying	Jendouba (TN)	Fruits, vegetables and fish
	Mukurweini (KE)	Tree tomato
	Kilombero (TZ)	Vegetables
	Kajjansi/Masaka (UG)	Fish
	Nakaseke (UG)	Eggplant

Milling	Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Legumes, cereals, and dried vegetable blended flours
	Laelay Machew (ET)	Moringa and teff
	Mukurweini, Kitui (KE)	Quinoa, tomato tree
	Mvomero, Morogoro (TZ)	Legumes and cereals blended flours
	Kamuli (UG)	Cereal, legume and orange-fleshed sweet potato flour
	Nakaseke (UG)	Fish bone powder
Smoking and fermentation	Nakaseke (UG)	Fish

Figure 1: Impact pathway

Descriptions of the different prototypes follow.

2. Osmotic dehydration and solar drying prototypes

2.1 Osmotic dehydration and solar drying of fruits and vegetables (Jendouba, TN)

2.1.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Many small-scale food producers, cooperatives, and agricultural development group (GDA) struggle with food preservation, especially in rural areas with limited access to advanced drying technologies. The main challenge is the rapid deterioration of fruits and vegetables due to high moisture content, leading to significant post-harvest losses. Traditional drying methods, such as open-air drying, are often inefficient and unhygienic, leaving the products vulnerable to contamination, mold growth, and nutrient loss. Additionally, these methods are time-consuming and do not provide consistent results, which limits the quality and shelf life of dried goods.

The open prototype of the solar dryer aims to address critical issues in food preservation, rural economic empowerment, and environmental sustainability. It tackles the challenge of post-harvest losses, particularly in high-moisture crops, by providing an affordable, energy-efficient solution for drying produce while maintaining nutritional quality and extending shelf life. The prototype aims to meet the needs of smallholder farmers, cooperatives, and agro-processors, offering them a means to reduce waste, increase incomes, and access new markets. Specific objectives include improving food security, reducing dependency on fossil fuels through solar energy, and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. Recognizing the role of women in food processing, the prototype targets gender inclusivity by empowering women with technology that enhances productivity and economic independence. This innovation also supports community resilience, environmental sustainability, and equitable access to resources, addressing both practical needs and broader development goals.

2.1.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The development of the solar dryer followed a structured Research and Innovation (R&I) pathway, grounded in scientific and technological criteria to

ensure its efficiency, usability, and sustainability. The process began with a thorough design phase, incorporating food-grade stainless steel to ensure safety and durability, and leveraging passive solar energy with enhanced airflow for optimal drying performance. Prototyping involved the construction of a modular and washable design to meet hygienic standards and facilitate easy maintenance.

The prototype was subjected to rigorous testing through controlled drying trials on high-moisture-content produce, including strawberries, tomatoes, peppers, onions, eggplants, fish and Bottarga. These trials incorporated pre-treatment methods like osmotic dehydration and dry salting to evaluate their effects on drying efficiency and product quality. Data collection focused on drying kinetics, moisture reduction, color retention, and texture preservation.

Validation included nutritional characterization of the products, ensuring the design addressed practical challenges and aligned with end-user needs. Energy efficiency and environmental sustainability were measured by tracking solar energy usage and evaluating cost savings. The final system was refined based on these insights, resulting in a robust and scalable solution ready for broader implementation.

2.1.3 Summary of the outputs

2.1.3.1 Results and achievements

The solar dryer (Figure 2.1.1) is an innovative food preservation technology designed to reduce post-harvest losses, improve food quality, and promote sustainability. It features a passive solar drying system with enhanced airflow and temperature control, constructed from food-grade stainless steel for safety and durability. The design includes a spacious drying chamber with nine removable and washable racks, ensuring hygiene and adaptability for various produce.

Figure 2.1.1: Solar dryer prototype

The dryer utilizes renewable solar energy, minimizing reliance on conventional energy sources and reducing operational costs. It is equipped to handle pre-treated produce, such as osmotic dehydrated or dry-salted fruits and vegetables, allowing for faster drying (Figure 2.1.2) while maintaining nutritional quality, texture, and color. Testing and validation have demonstrated its efficiency in drying high-moisture crops like strawberries, tomatoes, and peppers, significantly reducing drying time and energy consumption.

Figure 2.1.2: Moisture content evolution of eggplant slices during solar drying

Dry salting did not affect protein (9.08%), fat (0.48%) and potassium content (30890 ppm) of dried eggplant slices if compared to control.

2.1.3.2 Relevant production

Climate change as an asset to promote solar drying: An insight into drying characteristics and quality attributes of eggplant (*Solanum melongena L.*) (Paper under preparation).

2.1.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Jendouba (TN)	Osmotic dehydration and solar drying	20 farmers (women)

2.1.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Jendouba (TN)	Osmotic dehydration and solar drying	<p><u>Nutritional KPIs:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Decrease in moisture content, Vitamin C retention <p><u>Quality parameters</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Moisture content -Vitamin C content -Colour Retention

		<p>-Product texture</p> <p>-Rehydration ratio</p> <p>Renewable Energy Contribution:</p> <p>Solar Energy Production: Amount of energy generated by solar panels annually (target: 2779.5 KWh/year)</p> <p>Cost Efficiency: Energy Cost Savings: Reduction in energy costs due to solar energy integration (target: 312.08 USD/year).</p> <p>Product Range Expansion: 5 new dehydrated products will be introduced to the market.</p>
--	--	---

2.1.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

This section adopts an operational perspective to describe how to implement and manage the prototype, thus ensuring its full functionality and usability. It includes the deployment requirements, procedures, methods, techniques, and practical considerations.

2.1.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The solar dryer prototype is a sustainable food preservation solution designed for smallholder farmers, cooperatives, and agro-processors, addressing post-harvest losses and improving the quality and marketability of produce. Constructed from food-grade stainless steel, it features a spacious drying chamber with nine removable racks and utilizes passive solar energy with enhanced airflow and temperature control for efficient drying. The dryer is user-

friendly, modular, and compatible with pre-treatment methods such as osmotic dehydration and dry salting to reduce drying time and maintain product quality. It requires a sunny location, basic training for operation and maintenance, and manual monitoring to track drying progress. However, its performance can be constrained by weather dependency, limited drying capacity, and the upfront cost, which may require financial support for broader adoption. Despite these limitations, the prototype provides a scalable and environmentally friendly solution to improve food security and rural livelihoods.

2.1.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The prerequisites for the development and application of this prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Drying Chamber: Constructed from food-grade stainless steel, including frames and panels for durability and safety.	M
2	Racks: Removable and washable racks made of food-safe materials to hold produce during drying.	M
3	Solar Collector: Passive solar heating system for efficient energy absorption and airflow control.	M
4	Temperature and Humidity Control: Manual or basic monitoring equipment to track drying conditions.	1
5	Ventilation System: Optimized airflow mechanism for uniform drying, including vents or fans if necessary.	M
6	Assembly Tools: Basic tools for construction and maintenance of the dryer (e.g., drills, screws, welding tools).	1
7	Location Setup: Space with ample sunlight exposure and a stable surface for installation.	M
8	Raw Materials: Food-grade steel, insulation materials, and solar-grade glass or plastic for the collector.	M
9	Labor: Skilled personnel for design, assembly, and initial testing of the prototype.	1

10	Pre-Treatment Equipment: Containers, scales, and slicing tools for product pre-treatments like osmotic dehydration or dry salting.	2
11	Transportation: Logistics for delivering materials to the construction site.	2
12	Costs: Estimated budget of \$4,000 per unit for materials, construction, and assembly.	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.1.6.3 Implementation

The prototype implementation process, including indicative timeline, milestones, and any specific task associated with the innovation adoption are detailed below.

Month	Task	Milestone
March 2025	Project planning and stakeholder engagement.	Completion of detailed project roadmap with stakeholder roles clearly defined.
April 2025	Procurement of materials and equipment for the prototype	All necessary materials and tools secured for construction.
May 2025	Assembly and initial setup of the solar dryer prototype.	Fully assembled and functional prototype ready for testing.
June 2025	Testing and calibration of the dryer under controlled conditions.	Optimization of drying parameters based on initial trials.
July 2025	Training sessions for end-users on operation and maintenance.	End-users equipped with the necessary skills for proper usage.

August 2025	Field testing and validation of the dryer with local cooperatives.	Performance metrics collected, feedback incorporated into design.
September 2025	Refinement of the prototype based on feedback.	Improved and user-validated prototype finalized.
October 2025	Launch of pilot adoption with selected cooperatives.	Initial rollout of solar dryers to target user groups.
November 2025 – March 2026	Monitoring and evaluation of pilot usage, addressing challenges, and assessing impact	Comprehensive performance report and recommendations for scaling.
April 2026	Finalization of scaling strategy and market readiness.	Solar dryer production ready for larger-scale implementation.

2.1.6.4 Management

The management of the solar dryer innovation requires structured oversight, control, evaluation, and maintenance to ensure its effectiveness and sustainability. A dedicated project manager will oversee implementation, supported by a governance framework with clear roles for stakeholders, including cooperatives, manufacturers, and research partners. Monitoring and evaluation systems will track performance metrics such as drying efficiency, energy savings, and product quality, while regular field visits and user feedback will inform continuous improvement. Preventive maintenance schedules will ensure the durability of components, supported by accessible technical support and spare parts. Quality control measures will standardize drying processes and ensure compliance with food safety standards. Capacity-building efforts, including training sessions and user manuals, will empower users to maximize the dryer’s potential. Long-term sustainability will be supported through partnerships with local organizations and private-sector players, facilitating scaling, market access, and ongoing innovation.

2.1.7 Conclusions

The solar dryer represents a significant innovation in food preservation, particularly for smallholder farmers and cooperatives. It addresses critical issues such as post-harvest losses, energy inefficiency, and limited market access for agricultural products. By leveraging renewable solar energy and food-grade materials, the dryer offers a sustainable, cost-effective solution to extend the shelf life of fruits and vegetables while maintaining product quality. However, for widespread adoption, it is essential to consider organizational, operational, and policy factors that support its long-term success.

To ensure successful implementation and scalability, organizationally, multi-stakeholder collaborations are necessary, involving farmers, cooperatives, manufacturers, and policymakers. These partnerships will facilitate coordination, resource mobilization, and knowledge exchange. Operationally, it is crucial to establish user-friendly protocols for dryer operation, maintenance, and quality control. Additionally, training programs for users will be essential to maximize the dryer's potential. On the policy front, advocacy for renewable energy adoption and financial incentives for smallholder farmers, such as grants or subsidies, can help alleviate the initial investment barriers.

Future work could focus on technological improvements to enhance the dryer's performance. Incorporating sensors for automated temperature and humidity control would reduce the need for manual monitoring, improving ease of use. Moreover, integrating the dryer with IoT systems could provide real-time data collection and performance tracking, enabling better operational insights. Developing modular designs that allow for increased drying capacity or adaptability to different crops would make the technology more versatile and scalable. Additionally, further research could be undertaken to investigate more efficient solar materials, with a view of improving energy capture and reduce drying time. Further studies on nutrient retention and quality of dried produce could also be undertaken to help optimize pre-treatment and drying processes. Exploring hybrid solar-electric models could also be beneficial for regions with inconsistent sunlight, broadening the dryer's applicability.

Moving forward, a phased scaling strategy is anticipated, starting with pilot projects and progressing to broader commercialization. Continued collaborations with research institutions, private-sector players, and policymakers will be essential for refining the technology and expanding its reach. Aligning the solar dryer with sustainable development goals, such as food security, renewable energy, and rural development, will not only enhance its societal impact but also contribute to achieving broader environmental and economic benefits.

2.2 Tomato tree drying using Innovative Hybrid Solar Drier (Kitui, KE)

2.2.1 Prototype motivations and objectives

The prototype is a hybrid solar drier with a solar collector at the top through which air at ambient temperature circulated by a solar fan passes as it is forced through the drying cabinet containing stacked drying trays loaded with the food material before it comes out as exhaust air. Convex lenses fixed on the glass cover of the solar collector concentrate the solar radiation thus increasing the intensity of the radiation reaching the black absorber surface. In addition, the drier has a battery that is charged by solar energy and is used to heat the drying air and to power the air fan when there is inadequate or no solar radiation. This changeover from direct solar air heating to battery powered DC air heating is accomplished by a programmable logic controller. There is therefore extended drying period beyond that for a typical solar drier to achieve fast drying before the onset of microbial or chemical spoilage. This is especially important in the drying of fruits and vegetables, since they have high moisture content. The prototype is simple to operate and scalable. It has a drying compartment with a capacity of 6 trays of size 50 cm x 55 cm each holding a thin layer of 2.5 kg tree tomato pulp.

The innovation aims at helping small scale farmers and agro processors in reducing post-harvest losses as well as in value addition. Owing to the mode of operation, the dryer system will be capable of drying during the cold weather conditions and during the night. It is cheap and easy to operate therefore the technology can easily be adopted by small scale enterprises and farmers who are mostly women and youth.

The objectives of the tomato tree solar drying activities were to:

- Design and construct an innovative prototype hybrid indirect solar cabinet drier.
- Compare the performance of the hybrid solar drier and an existing solar tunnel drier.
- Determine the effect of solar drying technology on the quality of tree tomato powder
- Determine the economic feasibility of a tree tomato pulp solar drying system incorporating the innovative hybrid indirect solar cabinet drier.
- Assess the acceptance of the hybrid indirect solar cabinet drier by stakeholders (farmers/SMEs).

2.2.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

An innovative prototype hybrid indirect solar cabinet drier was designed and constructed in the University of Nairobi Agricultural Engineering workshop. The innovative solar drier and the existing solar tunnel drier were used for drying tree tomato and compared in terms of drying characteristics. Variation of moisture content with time was determined and the data fitted to equations to determine the model parameters and the goodness of fit. After tree tomato drying, the dry product was milled into powder, packaged and analysed to determine characteristics. Pilot validation of the innovative drying technology was done at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited (KEPC) premises in Kitui Town, Kitui Food Hub to demonstrate the operation of the solar drying system and to assess the acceptance of the technology using standard technology acceptance questionnaire.

Over 40 people who included local farmers and processors were able to learn about the new technology during the validation process. Participating farmers were exposed to the entire process used for making tree tomato powder, from tomato cleaning, pulping, drying, milling and packaging. Feedback on the innovative solar drier and the drying process was collected from the respondents on the conducted activities, outputs reached, outcomes and impact of the innovative technology.

2.2.3 Summary of the outputs

2.2.3.1 Results and achievements

The innovative hybrid solar drier was compared with a solar tunnel drier to determine its effectiveness in drying of tree tomato pulp. Variation of the moisture content on a dry weight basis) of tree tomato with time was obtained for both types of solar dyers (Figure 2.2.1 and 2.2.2). The data was fitted into a number of thin layer drying models to obtain an equation that best fits the progression of the drying process. For both dyers, the Modified Page Model presented in Equation 1 was the best:

$$MR = \exp(-(kt)^n) \quad \text{Eqn 1}$$

Where MR is the ratio of the moisture content on a dry weight basis at any given time to the equilibrium moisture content at the prevailing temperature and relative humidity, t is time in hours, and k and n are constants.

The values of k and n for the innovative hybrid solar dryer were 0.116 and 8.128 respectively while for the solar tunnel dryer they were 0.146 and 4.022 respectively.

Figure 2.2.1: Modified Page model vs experimental data for the innovative hybrid solar dryer

Figure 2.2.2: Modified Page model prediction vs experimental data for the solar tunnel dryer

Effect of the Solar Drying Technologies on the Quality of Tree Tomato Powder

Effect of Solar tunnel (ST) and Innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer (ISD) driers on quality of tree tomato powder

There was no significant difference in the L^* , a^* , b^* , c^* and ΔE^* values. The drying system only significantly affected the h^* value of the fruit powder which was higher for the ST (30.33) compared to the ISD (25.63) dryer.

There was no significant difference ($p < 0.001$) between the two dryers in moisture content ($8.66 \pm 0.00\%$ and $8.85 \pm 0.018\%$ for ISD and ST respectively) and water activity (0.41) of the tree tomato powders. The average pH value was significantly ($p < 0.001$) different with higher values recorded on the solar tunnel (3.88) as compared to the innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer (3.86).

Table 2.2.1 shows the technological quality parameters of the tree tomato powder from both dryers. It can be deduced that dryer difference did not have significant effect on rehydration ratio and water activity of the powder product. Significant difference ($p < 0.001$) was recorded on the water solubility % at 50°C with higher

value of 98.53 for the solar tunnel dryer and 97.68 innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer. There was no significant difference in the technological parameters rehydration ratio, hygroscopicity and water solubility (at 25°C and at 80°C) ($p>0.05$).

Flavonoids were higher (4.18) in the solar tunnel dryer as compared with the innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer which recorded a value of 3.96. The average antioxidant activity (mg/100 g) for the innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer was 1672.37 while that from solar tunnel was 1661.10. The beta carotene and vitamin C contents were significantly ($p<0.001$) different between the two dryers, with higher values of beta-carotene and vitamin C (mg/100 g) recorded in the innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer (48.77, 348.89) as compared to the solar tunnel dryer (45.48, 338.02).

The sensory analysis results showed the innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer (ISD) drier product was superior to that from the tunnel dryer in terms of appearance, aroma, taste and general acceptability with an average score of 4.3, 4.59, 4.81, 4.78, and 4.95 as compared to the solar tunnel drier which recorded 3.83, 4.4, 4.43, 4.54 and 4.4 respectively on a 5-point hedonic scale.

Innovative Solar Dryer Side View

Innovative Solar Dryer- Compartment opened

Tree tomato pulp drying

Tree tomato leather

Tree tomato powder at Kitui Hub

Figure 2.2.3: Innovative hybrid solar dryer photographs during validation at Kitui Food Hub

Economic analysis

The economic feasibility of using the innovative solar drier to produce tree tomato powder was assessed. Table 2.2.1 shows the investment costs.

Table 2.2.1: Investment costs

ITEM	COST (US\$)
25 solar driers	24,225
Fruit pulper	620
Batch pasteurizer	1,163
Fruit washing trough	388
Attrition mill	388

The results of economic analysis are shown in Table 2.2.2.

Table 2.2.2: Economic analysis results

PARAMETER	VALUE
Production cost per kg powder (US\$)	11.79
Selling price per kg powder (US\$)	14.0
Benefit-Cost ratio	1.19
Return on Investment – ROI (%)	18.75
Profit margin (%)	15.79

The results of economic analysis in Table 2.2.2 show that investment in prototype size innovative solar drier together with the associated equipment required to wash the tree tomato fruits, pulp the fruits, pasteurize the pulp and mill the dry tree tomato pulp leather is economically feasible.

Technology acceptance

Validation of the tree powder production technology was done at the Kenya Enterprise Promotion Company Limited factory premises located within the Kitui Food Hub. The production process was demonstrated to the local farmers and the factory personnel. A standard technology acceptance questionnaire was completed by 37 respondents and the results are shown in Table 2.2.3. The majority of the respondents were female (59.5%). Age distribution was as follows: Less than 30 years – 2.7%, 30-39 years – 2.7%, 40-49 years – 21.6%, 50-60 years – 27.1% and >60 years – 21.6%.

Table 2.2.3: Tree tomato powder production technology acceptance

ACCEPTANCE PARAMETERS	LIKELY						UNLIKELY
	Extremely	Quite	Slightly	Neither	Slightly	Quite	Extremely

Using this technology would be useful in preserving tree tomato fruit	91.9	5.4	0	0	0	0	2.7
Using this technology would increase the market for tree tomato fruits	86.5	13.5	0	2.9	0	0	0
Using this technology would reduce tree tomato losses	89.2	8.1	0	2.7	0	0	0
Using this technology would lead to increased use of tree tomato in new food products	97.3	2.7	0	0	0	0	0
Using this technology would increase farmers' income	89.2	10.8	0	0	0	0	0
Learning to operate this technology would be easy for me	83.8	13.5	2.7	0	0	0	0

I would find the tree tomato powder production technology easy to use	89.2	8.1	2.7	0	0	0	0
I have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available	89.2	8.1	0	0	0	0	2.7

All the technology acceptance parameters were reported to be “likely extremely” by 83.8-97.3% of respondents while a further 2.7-13.5% of the respondents reported that the technology acceptance parameters are “quite likely”. Only one respondent (2.7%) found the technology acceptance extremely unlikely.

2.2.3.2 Relevant production

The following manuscripts are under preparation.

1. Shelf life studies of tree tomato powder stored at ambient temperature in different packaging materials
2. Effect of solar tunnel and innovative hybrid solar cabinet dryer on Functional properties of tree tomato powder

2.2.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation	n. farmers / SMEs
----------	------------	-------------------

	(new technology / system / tool / food product)	
Kitui	Cabinet solar drier incorporating radiation concentration	37 farmers

2.2.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kitui	Cabinet solar drier incorporating radiation concentration	Drying time reduced by 100% due to incorporation of a battery operated air heater.
		A 18.75% Return-on-Investment (ROI)
		Over 90% of the respondents who participated in the validation exercise have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available.

2.2.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

2.2.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The prototype is a solar drier with a solar collector at the top through which air at ambient temperature passes as it is forced through the drying cabinet containing stacked drying trays loaded with the food material before it comes out as exhaust air. In addition, the drier has a battery that is charged by solar energy and is used to heat the drying air when there is inadequate or no solar radiation. There is therefore extended drying period beyond that for a typical

solar drier. The user has to prepare the food material for drying, for example washing, pulping and heat treatment of the tree tomato pulp before loading it on the drying trays and putting the trays in the drying cabinet racks.

The major limitation of the present prototype solar drier is that the air fan has low capacity and therefore the air circulation is limited thus adversely affecting the drying rate.

2.2.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

Prerequisites for developing and implementing the prototypes are given below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Solar panel (US\$ 194)	M
2	Battery (US\$ 194)	M
3	Drying chamber and stand (US\$ 233)	M
4	Auxiliary components like fan, pipes, sensors. Wiring (US\$ 155)	M
5	Labour (US\$ 194)	M
6	Availability of skilled manpower for dryer fabrication	M
7	Reliable raw materials supply	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.2.6.3 Implementation

Step 0: Knowledge about the market, user needs etc...

Milestone: Market study report

Timeline: 3 months

Tasks: Market survey

Step 1: Possession of technologies and appropriate tools

Milestone: Research and development report

Timeline: 6 months

Tasks: Development, testing and validation of the solar drier.

Milestone: Manufacturing plant design report

Timeline: 2 months

Tasks: Manufacturing plant, equipment and layout design

Milestone: Economic evaluation report

Timeline: 1 month

Tasks: Costing of civil works, building, equipment, personnel, raw materials, energy, overheads. and performing an economic appraisal to determine the profitability of the proposed venture.

Milestone: Procurement of equipment/tools

Timeline: 3 months

Tasks: Getting quotations and placing, placing orders and delivery by suppliers.

Milestone: Installation of equipment and commissioning

Timeline: 3 months for an existing building, 9 months for a new building.

Tasks: Installation of equipment and commissioning in an existing or new building.

Step 2: Procurement of suitable quantities of raw materials and components from accredited/recognised suppliers

Milestone: Raw materials and components procured.

Timeline: 2 months

Tasks: Getting quotations, placing orders and delivery by suppliers.

Step 3: Solar drier production in a standardised environment

Milestone: Solar drier production

Timeline: 1 month

Tasks: Production and testing of the solar driers

2.2.6.4 Management

An optimum number of personnel should be employed by the solar drier production enterprise, with a competent manager/supervisor. Training in the necessary skills is essential. Production, maintenance, quality control and marketing are key areas of focus.

2.2.7 Conclusions

A hybrid indirect cabinet solar drier has been designed, constructed and tested. The prototype is a hybrid solar drier with a solar collector at the top through which air at ambient temperature circulated by a solar fan passes as it is forced through the drying cabinet containing stacked drying trays loaded with the food material before it comes out as exhaust air. Convex lenses fixed on the glass cover of the solar collector concentrate the solar radiation thus increasing the intensity of the radiation reaching the black absorber surface. In addition, the drier has a battery that is charged by solar energy and is used to heat the drying air and to power the air fan when there is inadequate or no solar radiation. This changeover from direct solar air heating to battery powered DC air heating is accomplished by a programmable logic controller. There is therefore extended drying period beyond that for a typical solar drier to achieve fast drying before the onset of microbial or chemical spoilage especially for drying fruits and vegetables with high moisture content. The solar drying system is economically viable and acceptable to stakeholders. The prototype is simple to operate and is scalable. The potential users are food business operators and farmers. This technology can be commercialised, but to further enhance performance efficiency, additional research and development to increase the air flow rate is worth considering. An industrial processing plant should be optimally designed and evaluated for profitability. At the national level, policies and standards should be developed to promote the manufacture of solar driers.

2.3 Eggplant drying (Nakaseke, UG)

2.3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) is an important vegetable in Nakaseke area and was identified for promotion in the Nakaseke-Kapeka FoodLAND Food Hub. Like other vegetables, eggplants deteriorate quite fast, resulting in post-harvest loss. Currently, farmers and value-chain actors lack protocols that can be used to extend the shelf-life for eggplant. The objective of this work was to develop and promote a drying prototype for extending the shelf-life of eggplant. Drying is a relatively easy to use and inexpensive preservation technology that is suitable for resource constrained farmers and other value-chain actors. Solar drying, in particular takes advantage of free energy (sunshine) and the equipment required is inexpensive. While solar dryers are available in Nakaseke area and used for drying some commodities such as mangoes and bananas, their use for preservation of vegetables, including eggplant is dismal. One problem experienced when drying eggplants is browning. Appropriate pretreatments can be used to be used to overcome this problem.

2.3.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Experiments were conducted to compare effect of different pre-treatments (blanching and sodium metabisulphite treatment) and drying treatments (solar, oven and refractance window drying) on dried eggplant properties, with a view of establishing the conditions to promote. Eggplants subjected to different pre-treatment and drying conditions were analysed for proximate composition and phytochemicals content. Drying times for the three drying methods were determined by taking samples at regular intervals until constant weight was recorded. The least time to achieve moisture <10% and pretreatment that effectively controlled browning were selected for use.

To promote solar drying of eggplants, a total of 25 persons, consisting of NGO staff and farmers from Nakaseke were trained on the technology. The protocol for solar drying of egg plants was also printed and disseminated.

Eggplant dried using solar drying was analysed for market potential for determining consumers' willingness to pay. Dried samples were also cooked and their sensory acceptance compared to that of cooked fresh eggplant. Data collection was from 46 people living in Kampala.

2.3.3 Summary of the outputs

2.3.3.1 Results and achievements

The protocol entails slicing eggplants to thickness of 2 mm, blanching (85°C for 2 minutes) and dipping in a solution of sodium metabisulphite (5% for 5 minutes) followed by drying using solar, oven or refractance window dryer to a stable moisture content. Dried eggplants contained 3.02 (%) protein, 3.65 (%) crude fibre, 8.81 (%) ash, 3.90 (%) carbohydrates, 166.44 (mg GAE/100 g) phenolics, 35.91 (mg CatE/100g) flavonoids, 8.31 (mg CatE/100g) tannins and total antioxidant activity of 44.01 (mg AAE/100g). Dried egg plants stored in polyethylene bags are shelf-stable beyond 12 months. In the willingness to pay assessment, 89.1% of respondents indicated willingness to pay the estimated cost price or higher for the dried eggplants. Sensory scores for the dry eggplant were significantly inferior to those for cooked fresh eggplant, though both were generally acceptable. A total of 58.3% of the respondents preferred the fresh cooked eggplant to the dry one and 41.7% preferred the dry eggplant.

2.3.3.2 Relevant production

Nagudi, R. Preservation of eggplant (*Solanium melongena*) by drying. B.Sc. Research project Makerere University. Under preparation.

2.3.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation	n. farmers / SMEs
----------	------------	-------------------

	(new technology / system / tool / food product)	
Nakaseke	Solar drying of eggplant	1 SME, 25 farmers

2.3.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Nakaseke	Solar drying of eggplant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Percentage reduction in eggplant postharvest loss ● Percentage increase in consumers that are able to access of eggplant off season ● Number of farmers and SMEs able to preserve eggplant ● Percentage of farmers and traders reporting improved market access for eggplant

2.3.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

2.3.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Solar drying for eggplants could be done household level, group level or by commercial businesses, with the different levels requiring different dryer capacities. The dryers to be used can be selected from different solar dryers available. Thus, the focus of the activities on solar drying of eggplant do not focus on equipment, rather on the application of solar drying technology to eggplants.

For maintain steady drying operations, reliable supply of raw materials is required and the eggplants should be handled using recommended post-harvest

processes to avoid quality loss. Pre-treatments to limit browning during eggplant drying are also critical for ensuring acceptable product appearance. After drying, it is important to package the products in containers with moisture proof containers. A key limitation for solar drying is the slow drying rate recorded during periods of limited sunshine. This can be overcome by complementing solar drying with other drying techniques, like biomass or electric oven drying.

2.3.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The prerequisites for the development and implementation of the prototype are provided below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Sunshine	M
2	Proximity to raw material sources	1
3	Dryer construction capacity	M
4	Appropriate product packaging	1
5	Proper handling of raw materials	1

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

2.3.6.3 Implementation

This section outlines the implementation process, including indicative timeline, milestones, and any specific task associated with the innovation adoption.

Phase 0 - Institutional arrangements for operationalisation of eggplant drying

Tasks

Farmers, farmer groups and SMEs decide to adopt eggplant drying

Farmers, farmer groups and SMEs determine where to conduct eggplant drying and aims (own consumption, local sales, sales to nearby cities or national sales)

Farmers, farmer groups and SMEs decide on model to be used for eggplant drying and product distribution/ marketing

Milestone

Operational model of eggplant drying established

Phase 1: Acquisition of dryers for different operators

Tasks

Determining of dryer capacity requirements

Identification of dryer designs that match capacity requirements and available budgets

Procurement or fabrication of dryers

Milestone

- Food operators get access to dryer to be used for eggplant drying

Phase 2: Food operators produce dry eggplant

Tasks

Food operators apply developed drying process using procured dryers

Milestone

Food operator produced dry eggplant products

Phase 3 - Test marketing of eggplant

Tasks

Production of samples for test marketing

Determination of market requirements and market potential size

Development of marketing plan

Milestone

Market plan based on test marketing results

Phase 4 - Commercial eggplant drying

Tasks

Identification and deployment of production staff

Design of appropriate product packaging

Large scale eggplant drying and packaging

Dry eggplant promotion, marketing and distribution

Milestone

At least 1 SME or farmer group producing and marketing dry eggplant

Dry eggplant widely available to public for purchase

Public aware of how to utilise eggplant in their diet

2.3.6.4 Management

The prototype has been disseminated to farmers, an SME and a non-governmental organisation. A general project dissemination event was also used to disseminate the protocol to some policy makers. In partnership with the SME partner (Nutreal) the prototype has been used to produce dry eggplant that is undergoing test marketing.

2.3.7 Conclusions

The drying process developed is suitable for preservation of eggplant and has potential to address the challenge of post-harvest eggplant post-harvest losses. Achieving wide acceptance of dry eggplant may, however, be a challenge since the culture of consuming preserved vegetables is relatively under developed in Uganda. It is desirable that the NGO and SME partner commit to continue to champion the use of this technology even after closure of the project.

2.4 Fish solar drying (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)

2.4.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Fresh fish is highly perishable, thus susceptible to post-harvest loss. Drying has been widely used for preservation of fish but the quality of some dried fish products is wanting. The objective of this activity was to develop a protocol for solar drying of fish to produce quality products from fish species available in Uganda.

2.4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Two live fish species (Nile tilapia and catfish) were obtained from fish farms in Pakwach and Zombo district, in northern Uganda. The fish was taken to Panyamur where the solar drier (Figure 5) had been installed. Solar drying of fish was done in accordance with Masette (2013). Fish was split, thoroughly washed and then sliced into thinner portions (10 mm thickness) to facilitate the drying process. The fish was drip dried in the shade for 2-3 hours to avoid case hardening. These portions were first spread on a drying rack at ambient temperatures (26 – 30°C) before being transferred to the tent for further drying. The fish pieces in the tent solar dryer were turned at regular (1 hour) intervals and dried for approximately 2 – 4 days. The temperature in the tent solar drier was between 35-40°C. Dried samples for the two species (Nile tilapia, catfish) were transported to the food processing plant at Food Biosciences and Agribusiness Research Program (FBA), National Agricultural Research Laboratories, Kawanda which is one of the NARO institutes with facilities for product development. At Kawanda, the sun-dried Tilapia was prepared for shelf life study. Assessments included; physico-chemical (moisture content, water activity), microbial (total viable count, yeast and mould count) and sensory analysis (9-point Hedonic scale). Sensory evaluation of the different processed fish was carried out according to Santana et al. (2015) by 10 trained panelists from National Agricultural Research Laboratories, Kawanda, aged between 20-60 years.

Figure 2.4.1: Solar tent used for drying of the fish

2.4.3 Summary of the outputs

2.4.3.1 Results and achievements

All the dried fish samples had moisture content below the UNBS/EAS acceptable level of 15% for dried fish products. Average scores for different sensory acceptability properties were in the range 4-6 on the 9 point hedonic scale. Solar dried tilapia had borderline sensory acceptability (5.4) while solar dried catfish was not liked (3.9). This shows that the dried fish was not well liked by consumers. This could be because the dried fish products were relatively new to the consumers. Microbial counts (yeast and mould count) was within acceptable limits during the eight week storage period. Overall, the solar drying technology was able to extend the shelf life of dried fish products by at least four weeks which is the recommended minimum threshold (Mustapha *et al.*, 2014). It is envisaged that promotion and increased awareness of dried fish products from large pelagic fish will lead to greater consumption and acceptability akin to the smoked products.

2.4.3.2 Relevant production

Tinyiro S. E., Masette M., Akullo D., Wanda F. and Aruho C. Shelf-life assessment of improved primary processed Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and African catfish (*Clarius gariepinus*) products. 3rd FAR4ViBE Scientific Conference, Arusha, Tanzania 29th – 31st October 2024.

2.4.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Solar drying of tilapia and African catfish	5 farmers

2.4.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Solar drying of tilapia and African catfish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 10% reduced loss of fresh fish -increased shelf life through preservation using solar • Increased income by at least 20% for fish processors/farmers

2.4.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

2.4.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The initial set up/construction of the solar tent dryer requires specialised engineering knowledge and practical skills. The site or location of the solar tent dryer should be near the source of raw material, on elevated ground with easy access to sunlight and natural air drift. Mostly, locally available materials can be used in the construction. Prerequisite programs especially good hygienic practices are important to have the best raw material entering the solar tent. In addition, users should pay attention to the thickness of fish slices and spacing on

the racks in the solar tent. Routine turning of the fish slices is important to ensure uniform drying.

The solar tent dryer is more effective with plenty of sunshine (dry conditions). It can be used at community level, usually fish processor groups.

The major limitation of the technology is dependent on prevailing weather, whereby sunny conditions are required. This could be improved by provision of supplementary heating such as use of biomass etc. In addition, the covered nature of the tent limits natural air flow and thus forced air may be required to hasten the drying process.

2.4.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The prerequisites for the development and implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials: Quality fresh fish handled well (Good Hygienic Practices) Nearby raw material source – lake, river, fish pond</i>	1
2	<i>Equipment: Well-constructed solar tent dryer in ideal location</i>	1
3	<i>Energy: Sunlight</i>	1
4	<i>Others: Potable water for washing</i>	1
* <i>Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low</i>		

2.4.6.3 Implementation

This section outlines the implementation process, including indicative timeline, milestones, and any specific task associated with the innovation adoption.

No	Activity	Mile stones	Months					
			1	2	3	4	5	6

1	Baseline/Market survey (Knowledge about the market, user needs) and stakeholder mapping	Information on value chain actors/stakeholders and market requirements						
2	Procurement of raw materials, equipment and other inputs from prequalified suppliers	Raw materials, equipment and other inputs in place						
3	Solar tent drying of fish – testing and optimising conditions with fish processor groups (end-user setting) at pilot level	Solar tent drying protocols and process conditions optimised Solar dried products developed and profiled						
4	Market testing of solar tent dried fish	Market test reports and customer feedback						
5	Scaling/Uptake of solar drying technology at commercial scale	Private sector-led commercial production of solar dried fish (At least 1 SME) UNBS certified dried fish products on the market						

2.4.6.4 Management

The solar tent drying technology requires a well-constructed solar dryer. In addition implementers/users should adhere to established prerequisite programs (especially Good Hygienic Practices), SOPs, protocols and work flows. More so, a quality management system based on HACCP has to be put in place to ensure

continuous production of quality and safe solar dried fish products. Initial training of production staff on maintenance and operations of the solar tent dryer is important for building local capacity. A program for continuous technical backstopping through scheduled monitoring visits by the technical team will help to keep operations on track.

2.4.7 Conclusions

The solar tent drying technology was used to develop solar dried products from Nile tilapia and catfish with acceptable shelf life. The technology can go a long way towards solving challenges of open sun drying of fish such as long drying time, susceptibility to contamination and drudgery. To limit dependence of weather and to ensure even faster drying, modifications such as incorporation of a fan/ extractor to enable forced air movement and use of supplementary heat source could be considered.

References

- Masette M. (2013). Securing the nutritional value of freshwater fish products in the East, Central and Southern African region: Case study for Uganda. FAO Report
- Mustapha, M. K., Ajibola, T. B., Salako, A. F., & Ademola, S. K. (2014). Solar drying and organoleptic characteristics of two tropical African fish species using improved low-cost solar driers. *Food science & nutrition*, 2(3), 244-250.
- Santana, P., Huda, N., & Yang, T. A. (2015). Physicochemical properties and sensory characteristics of sausage formulated with surimi powder. *Journal of food science and technology*, 52, 1507-1515.

2.5 Vegetables drying (Kilombero, TZ)

2.5.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Fruits and vegetables are essential components of the human diet, providing vital micronutrients, vitamins, minerals, and enzymes. Due to their high water content and moisture activity, vegetables are particularly prone to microbial spoilage and degradation caused by biochemical processes such as enzymatic activity, respiration, and senescence. To mitigate these risks, methods that reduce water activity are employed, with solar drying or dehydration being among the most effective. Solar drying removes moisture from vegetables, inhibiting biochemical reactions and preventing microbial growth, thereby extending shelf life and ensuring availability even during off-seasons. This prototype aims to address the critical challenge of preserving vegetables through the use of solar drying technology. The specific objectives include developing an efficient, sustainable drying solution that reduces spoilage, enhances shelf life, and ensures the year-round availability of vegetables. Solar drying, which harnesses renewable energy, is a key method for lowering the moisture content of vegetables, thus preventing microbial growth and halting undesirable biochemical processes. In terms of gender considerations, the design and implementation of the prototype aim to be accessible to all, particularly for women, especially those in the Kilombero Food Hub. The aim is to ensure that the technology can be easily adopted and effectively used by women in the region. By offering a low-cost, environmentally friendly solution, the prototype empowers women farmers and food processors, enabling them to preserve vegetables more efficiently, increase their income, and reduce postharvest losses in their communities. This prototype focuses on three widely consumed vegetables (amaranthus, cassava leaves, and sweet potato leaves) commonly found in the food hubs and selected for this study.

2.5.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Selection of vegetables

In collaboration with farmers and food processors in Kilombero Food Hub, three types of commonly consumed vegetables were selected for this project. The vegetables were selected based on local production, availability and cost as

compared to other vegetables. The selected vegetables are (a) Amaranthus, (b) cassava, and (c) sweat potato leaves (Figure 2.5.1).

Figure 2.5.1. Fresh vegetables at Kilombero Food Hub market

(a) amaranthus, (b) sweat potato leaves and (c) cassava leaves.

Drying of vegetables

The selected vegetables were washed with clean water and blanched in hot water at 75°C for 3 minutes. Then the vegetables were dried in a walk-in solar dryer for 48 hours at a temperature between 30 and 50°C. The dried vegetables (Figure 2.5.2) were ground into powders and analyzed for folic acid according to Sandip et al. (2017), phytochemical content as described by Okiki et al. (2015), oxalate ions as per AOAC (1998), tocopherol/vitamin E content (Fidanza 1991), and total phenolic and flavonoid content according to Saeed et al. (2019). The detailed methodology and results were reported in the characterization section (Task 4.6).

Figure 2.5.2. Dried vegetables ((a) amaranthus, (b) sweat potato leaves and (c) cassava leaves)

2.5.3 Summary of the outputs

2.5.3.1 Results and achievements

The walk-in solar dryer was designed to quickly dry vegetables, reducing post-harvest losses and enhancing the quality of fruits and vegetables. This technology was incorporated into the prototype to optimize drying efficiency. The walk-in solar dryer is a large, enclosed structure that uses solar energy to dry fruits and vegetables. It allows users to easily walk inside for convenient handling of the items being dried. The dryer harnesses sunlight through passive heat, reducing the reliance on electricity or fuel. It is an energy-efficient and environmentally friendly solution, particularly effective in preserving fruits and vegetables and minimizing post-harvest losses in areas with abundant sunlight, such as Kilombero food hub. Testing and validation have demonstrated its effectiveness in drying vegetables like amaranthus, sweet potato, and cassava leaves while preserving their nutritional quality. The results of the nutritional composition of vegetables dried in the walk-in solar dryer are presented in D5.16.

2.5.3.2 Relevant production

Potential of Walk-in Solar Dryers in Reducing Post-Harvest Losses and Improving Vegetable Quality in Tanzania: A Case Study of Kilombero Food Hubs (Manuscript in preparation).

2.5.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kilombero (TZ)	Solar drying	20 women farmers and processors

2.5.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kilombero	Solar drying	<p><u>Nutritional</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in moisture content, - Improve quality of final products - Increase shelf-life of vegetables <p><u>Energy saving:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in energy costs due to utilization of direct solar energy <p><u>New product development</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three new vegetables powered will be available to the market.

2.5.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

2.5.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The scope of the walk-in solar dryer prototype focuses on providing an efficient and sustainable solution for drying vegetables, aiming to reduce post-harvest losses and improve the quality of products. It is designed for use in regions with abundant sunlight, such as Kilombero Food Hub in Tanzania, where farmers and food processors can benefit from this innovative drying method. The prototype features a walk-in design that allows users to easily access and handle the items being dried, such as amaranth, cassava, and sweet potato leaves. It operates primarily on solar energy, utilizing both passive heat to reduce dependence on electricity or fuel, making it an eco-friendly and energy-efficient option. Users interact with the system by loading the vegetables into the dryer, monitoring the drying process, and ensuring proper airflow and rotation to maintain consistent drying conditions. However, the prototype has some limitations, such as its

reliance on consistent sunlight, which may reduce efficiency on cloudy or rainy days. Additionally, its drying capacity may be limited, making it less suitable for large-scale operations. The initial construction cost and the need for regular maintenance to ensure optimal performance also present potential barriers for widespread adoption.

2.5.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

Prerequisites for development and implementation of the prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Wood: <i>For construction of walk-in solar drier</i>	M
2	Clear polyethylene plastic: <i>To retain heat and moisture, maintaining a consistent temperature and humidity level inside the dryer</i>	M
3	Black plastic: <i>To capture, retain heat effectively and maintaining high temperatures</i>	M
4	Food-grade mesh: <i>For proper Air Circulation and Ventilation and for easy handling of vegetables</i>	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.5.6.3 Implementation

The implementation process for the walk-in solar dryer at Kilombero Food Hub involves several key phases, each with specific tasks and milestones to ensure successful adoption of the innovation.

Phase 1 – Planning and design:

- *Milestone: Completion of design and procurement of materials.*
- *Timeline: 2 months*
- *Tasks: Identifying stakeholders (farmers and food processors)*

Phase 2 – Identifying types of vegetables:

- Milestones: Identification and collection of vegetables
- Time line: 3 months
- Tasks: Collection and storage of vegetables.

Phase 3 – Pilot testing and optimization:

- Milestones: Testing results, performance optimization, and adjustments to the system.
- Timeline: 2 months
- Tasks: Test small batches of vegetables, evaluating the dryer’s efficiency, and optimization of drying conditions.

Phase 4 – Training and adoption (1-2 months):

- Milestones: Training and feedback collection from farmer/ processors.
- Timeline: 2 months
- Tasks: Training of farmers and food processors and preparing user manuals.

2.5.6.4 Management

The management of the walk-in solar dryer innovation involves structured oversight, control, evaluation, and maintenance to ensure its effectiveness and long-term sustainability. A designated farmer/processor group leader will oversee the implementation of the innovation, ensuring proper coordination and execution. Monitoring and evaluation systems will track key performance indicators, such as drying efficiency, energy usage, and product quality, enabling data-driven adjustments. Preventive maintenance schedules will help preserve the durability of the dryer’s components, supported by accessible technical assistance and readily available spare parts. Quality control measures will standardize the drying processes, ensuring consistency and adherence to food safety standards. Capacity-building efforts, including hands-on training sessions and detailed user manuals, will empower users with the necessary skills and knowledge to maximize the dryer’s functionality, and preserve the quality of vegetables.

2.5.7 Conclusions

In conclusion, the walk-in solar dryer prototype represents an innovative and sustainable solution to addressing the challenges of post-harvest losses in vegetable preservation, particularly in regions like Kilombero Food Hub in Tanzania. By harnessing solar energy, the dryer effectively reduces moisture content in vegetables, thereby inhibiting microbial growth and slowing biochemical processes that lead to spoilage. The technology not only improves the shelf life and quality of vegetables but also offers an energy-efficient and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional drying methods. The implementation process, from design to adoption, includes key phases such as vegetable selection, pilot testing, and capacity-building initiatives, ensuring the involvement of local farmers and food processors, particularly women. The project also emphasizes continuous monitoring and maintenance to guarantee long-term functionality and success. Through this innovation, the walk-in solar dryer is poised to reduce post-harvest losses, empower local communities, and contribute to food security and economic stability in the region.

References

- AOAC Official Method of Analysis, 15th ed. (1998). Official Methods of Analysis 19 Ed. Association of Analytical Chemists, Washington D.C
- Bano, T., Goyal, N., & Tayal, P. K. (2015). Innovative solar dryers for fruits, vegetables, herbs and ayurvedic medicines drying. *International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science*, 3(5), 883-888.
- Fidanza, F. (1991). *Nutritional status Assessment*. Chapman and Hall, London. Pp 210-211.
- Okiki, P.A., I.A.Osibote, O.Balogun, B.E. Oyinloye, O.Idris, Adelegan Olufunke, S.O.Asoso and P.T. Olagbemide (2015). Evaluation of Proximate, Minerals, Vitamins and Phytochemical Composition of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. *Advances in Biological Research* 9 (6):436-443,2015.
- Saeed, A., Muhammad Salim Marwat, Abdul Haleem Shah, Rubina Naz, Sheikh Zain-U-Abidin, Samina Akbar, Raees Khan, Muhammad Tariq Navid, Ahmad Saeed & Muhammad Zeeshan Bhatti (2019). Assessment of total phenolic and flavonoid contents of selected fruits and vegetables,

Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge Vol 18(4), October 2019, pp 686-693

- Sandip S. Kshirirsagar, Sachim M. Bhalekar, Dipali K. Gopale, Shirishkumar D. Ambavage (2017). Development and validation of New UV-Spectroscopic Method for water soluble Folic acid. International Journal of Chemical Concepts, Vol. 03, N0. 04, PP 364-370.

3. Milling

3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Milling is an important primary food processing technique used to transform agricultural materials into usable food products or ingredients for production of diverse products. Milling tasks were largely undertaken as part of procedures for production of raw materials, food ingredients or food products. Milling was conducted on different foods, including cereals, pseudocereals (grain amaranth and teff), legumes as well as dried fruits, vegetables and fish. Flour from the above materials were subjected to blending and/ or secondary processing, leading to different products, including nutrient-rich flours suitable for feeding of infants and children.

The specific objectives for the milling activities were to:

- I. To develop from local food raw materials blended flours suitable for direct use in preparation of foods that address nutrition needs of local communities
- II. To develop from local food raw materials nutrient and nutraceutical rich flours suitable for use as ingredients for processed foods
- III. To determine nutritional, nutraceutical, functionality, sensory and storage stability properties of milled products

Milling contributed to developing products for feeding of nutritionally vulnerable groups, like children. This of great relevance to women since women play the most important role in infant and early childhood feeding.

3.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Below (Table 3.1) is a list of the different products to which milling was applied and the corresponding Food Hubs.

Table 3.1. Raw materials from different food hubs used for milling studies

Food hub	Raw materials
Kondar/Chebika (TN)	Vegetables
Kondar/Chebika (TN)	Cereals and legumes
Laelay Machew (ET)	Moringa and teff
Mukurweiri/Kangundo (KE)	Tree tomato
Kitui (KE)	Quinoa
Mvomero, Morogoro (TZ)	Cereals and legumes
Kamuli (UG)	Beans, cereals, grain amaranth, sweet potatoes
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Fish bones

The activities involved in milling included selection of raw materials, cleaning of the raw materials to remove extraneous materials, drying or ensuring that the raw materials are dry, milling, blending (for cases leading to composite flours), packaging and flour analysis. Milling was done using widely available lab or commercial mills (mainly hammer mills).

Below are highlights of the processes used for the different products.

Milling and production of legume - cereals composite flours - Enfidha/Chebika (TN)

The selection of raw materials (wheat and legumes) was based on survey results about the agricultural products diversity in the food hub Enfidha/Chebika. Selected legumes were faba bean, chickpea and pea, they were subjected to different pretreatment (microwave and germination) and tested for nutritional properties (water content, crude proteins, phenolic content, antioxidant activity)

and functional properties (bulk density, tapped density, water and oil absorption capacities, swelling capacity...) and color parameters.

Composite flours Formulation: was based on mixing plane methodology generated by Expert Design 13 software that gives different formulations. Three substitution wheat flour levels were tested (10, 15 and 20%) using untreated, microwave heated and germinated legumes. Composite flours were subjected to the same analysis of raw material.

Based on the characterization results, one formulation of the composite flour of wheat and legumes was validated.

Milling and production of vegetable composite flours - Enfidha/Chebika (TN)

Vegetable blended composite flours were prepared from leaf powders (parsley, spinach and chard), bulb powders (potato and carrot), spices (tomato and onion) and wheat. Two particle sizes were tested (>0.5 mm and <0.5 mm). Different formulations were prepared using a D-optimal mixture experimental design and tested for their chemical, biochemical, physical and functional properties.

Protocol for milling and production of moringa and teff blended flours - Laelay Machew (ET)

Teff grains collected from 96 farmers that were involved in the precision harvesting innovative research in the 2023 crop season were milled using two different sieves to have coarse and fine milled teff flour in order to give chance for various value added products during the blending of teff flour with moringa leaves. Formulations were made using the following teff: moringa ratios: 90:10; 80:20; 70:30; 60:40; and 50:50.

The moringa leaves used for the study were collected from moringa plants that were planted in alley cropping systems with teff during the 2023 crop season. The 96 farmers that planted moringa with teff were the sources of the moringa leaves too. The moringa leaves are cleaned, dried and powdered using pestles by the farmers and we bought the powders from the beneficiary farmers. The moringa powders were transported to a laboratory at UoM laboratory and blended with the teff flour to obtain composites.

Protocol for milling and production of quinoa - Kitui (KE)

Quinoa grains were milled using hammer mills (Figure 3.1) at the Kitui food hub at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Ltd (KEPC). The fine flour strainer of the hammer was used for milling the quinoa grains. The milling was repeated 3 rounds to get a fine texture needed for preparation of mandazi. One round milling would be needed for flour used for porridge.

Figure 3.1: Mill used for milling quinoa (at KEPC)

Quinoa flour was used for blending with wheat, resulting in a blend suitable for making baked snacks (*mandazi*). The quinoa and wheat flour were blended in different ratios 34:66; 44:56; 54:46 and 70:30.

Protocol for milling and production of legumes, cereals and dry fruits blends - Mvomero/Morogoro (TZ)

The first stage involved selecting local raw materials for the production of blended composite flours. The materials chosen were white maize, millet, soybeans, biofortified common beans, sesame seeds, and sugar, each selected for its specific nutritional benefits. Millet was chosen to enhance the fiber content of the flour, while soybeans were included to boost the protein content. Biofortified common beans were selected for their high iron and zinc content, and white maize was chosen for its contribution to the energy content.

Four formulations were selected for testing based on locally available food ingredients and the WHO/UNICEF guidelines for total energy and protein content. In this study the Nutrisurvey software (2007) was used to generate the corresponding proportions of white maize, millets, soybeans, biofortified beans and sesame seeds in composite flour formulations and nutrient optimization. The nutrients optimised were protein, fat, fiber, zinc, iron, calcium, and vitamins A. The optimisation was done to ensure that each formulation provided more than 40% of the daily recommended intake in a single meal for children under two. The four blends were formulated in triplicates as shown in Table 3.2. Note: Three 3% sugar was included to enhance the taste of the final products.

Table 3.2. Ingredients and formulation for composite flour

Formulation	White maize (%)	Millet (%)	Soybean (%)	Biofortified common beans (%)	Sesame seeds (%)	Sugar for taste (%)
1	60	10	10	15	5	3
2	50	15	10	20	5	3
3	52	10	10	25	3	3
4	53	5	7	30	5	3

For each formulation, duplicate batches of blended composite flour were prepared. The ingredients were first cleaned and washed to remove any extraneous matter. Subsequently, they were dried in a hot air dryer at 60°C for 5

hours. Each ingredient was then separately milled using a Hammar mill (Figure 3.2), locally manufactured by Mzinga Holding Company Ltd, Morogoro, Tanzania. After milling, the ingredients were mixed together according to the formulation specified in Table 3.2, using an electric mixer. The resulting mixture was then sieved through a 0.6-1.0 mm mesh sieve and packaged in different packaging materials for laboratory analysis and shelf-life study. Details about composition and shelf-life are reported in other deliverables (D11, D13 and D16).

Figure 3.2. Hammer mill used for milling ingredients

Protocol for milling and production of legumes and cereals blended flours - Kamuli (UG)

Raw materials used included biofortified beans (NAROBAN 3), orange fleshed sweet potatoes (NASPOT 8), grain amaranth (cream type) and white maize. These crops were selected due to their nutritional value and availability among target farmers. The grains (maize, beans and grain amaranth) were milled in the natural dry form while orange fleshed sweet potatoes were first processed into dry slices before milling, using a locally fabricated hammer mill. The resulting flours were blended into formulations derived using response surface methodology designed to maximise iron and zinc content and to minimise

viscosity. The flours were analysed for proximate composition, in addition to the response variables (iron content, zinc content and gruel viscosity). Porridge from the flours were subjected to sensory evaluation. Market potential was evaluated by determining potential customers willingness to consume and pay for the product.

Protocol for milling and production of fish bone powder - Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)

Nile tilapia and African catfish carcasses were used as base material. By-products were separated into respective components (parts). The belly-flaps and all fatty material were removed from carcasses and washed with potable water at room temperature. Steaming was done at 80 °C for 15 minutes to inactivate enzymes and spoilage organisms and decrease the fat content. Oven drying was done at 60°C until brittle ($\leq 10\%$ moisture content). The content was crashed using a hammer mill made from food grade materials with a sieve mesh size of 0.5 mm. The process used for production of fish powder is summarised in Figure 3.2. The resultant powder was incorporated in maize grits in combination with other spices for the production of the extruded snack.

Figure 3.2. Preparation of fish powder

3.3 Summary of the outputs

3.3.1 Results and achievements

Results for the composition, functional properties and storage stability of flours produced from milling are reported in other deliverables (D5.11, D5.13 and D5.16). The results generally show blending other food materials with starchy staples led to products having superior nutritional value than that of the widely consumed starchy staples. Fish powder derived from milling was found to be

very high in the minerals calcium and phosphorous (Table 3.3) and can therefore be a good source for complementation of other foods with these nutrients.

Table 3.3. Micronutrient composition of fish powder

Product/Micronutrient composition	g/100g (%)		mg/kg (ppm)		
	P	Ca	Fe	Zn	Se
Fish powder from carcasses	9.31±1.5	17.4±2.8	71.91±3.1	45.15±1.8	1.25±0.2

3.3.2 Relevant productions

SUA

- Poster presentation at the FoodLAND annual meeting in Kampala.
- Two abstracts were submitted to the 9th STICE (Science, Technology, and Innovation Conference & Exhibition, September 11-13, 2024. Commission for Science and Technology Conference (COSTECH): Julius Nyerere International Conference Centre, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

UoN

- Potential contribution of Kenyan-grown quinoa to the diets of children aged 2-6 years. Under Review (Submitted to African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development (AJFAND))

Enfidha/Chebika (TN):

- Publication about the characterization of wheat and legumes composite flours is in progress.
- Publication about vegetables composite flours is planned.

Laelay Machew (ET)

- Gebreyohannes Girmay, Lemlem Weldegerima and Zenebe Gebreegziabher (2024). Characterization of Teff grain (*Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter)-Moringa (*Moringa olifera*, Lam) leaves composite flour, and seed oil for promoting operational nutrition in Ethiopia and Sub-Saharan Africa: in preparation.

Conferences/Exhibitions

UoN

- Poster on Quality of diets consumed by children aged 2-6 years in Kitui County. Annual Foodland Meeting, Kampala, Uganda, 17-19 January 2024.
- Poster on Quality of diets consumed by children aged 2-6 years in Kitui County. Nairobi Innovation Week (26 - 28 April, 2024).

3.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Mvomero (TZ)	Nutritious composite flour	20 and KTN (1 SMEs)
Kitui (KE)	Quinoa enriched porridge flour for feeding children from 2-6 years	40 farmers
Kitui (KE)	Tree tomato powder	40 farmers
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Composite flours (cereals / legumes / vegetables)	5 farmers, 2 SMEs, NGOs: GDA Kharroub Enfidha (12 operators) GDA Chebika (15 operators)

Laelay Machew (ET)	Teff-moringa blended flour	500 farmers
Laealy Machew (ET)	Moringa leaf powder preparation and supply	96 farmers
Kamuli (UG)	Orange-fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans and grain amaranth blended flour	1 SME
Nakaseke (UG)	Fish powder from carcasses	2 SMEs and 30 farmers

3.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Mvomero (TZ)	Nutritious composite flour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased business opportunity for SME - Improved access to nutritious composite flour - Increased access data especially shelf-life and nutritional compositions
Kitui (KE)	Quinoa enriched porridge flour for feeding children from 2-6 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diet diversification and improved nutrition status - Increased profitability for food business operators as reflected in a high benefit cost ratio and internal rate of return (IRR)
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Composite flours (cereals / legumes / vegetables)	<p>Health benefits: the new formulations could provide enhanced nutritional content.</p> <p>Economic impact:</p>

		<p>Introducing a new food formulation item can spark competition, resulting in fresh ideas and more options for consumers.</p> <p>Jobs can be created by the creation and production of new food formulations.</p> <p>Environmental impact:</p> <p>Waste reduction by shortening of the supply chain in the Food Hub. However, different agricultural resources may be required for the new formulation, potentially affecting land use, water consumption, and biodiversity.</p> <p>Social impact:</p> <p>Acceptance by consumers is important. Cultural preferences and eating habits can affect the success of a new formulation.</p>
Laelay Machew (ET)	Teff-moringa blended flour	<p>Increasing consumption of moringa leaf powder in Axum area (being considered as medicinal)</p> <p>New income streams for food operators (farmers and SMEs)</p>
Kamuli (UG)	Orange-fleshed sweet potato, biofortified beans and grain amaranth blended flour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhanced SME capacity in value addition - Business opportunity for SME - Improved access of consumers to nutrient rich products

		- Increased farmer access to market for agricultural produce
Nakaseke (UG)	Fish bone powder	At least 50% reduction in fish processing waste Fish powder rich in micronutrients namely; calcium, iron and zinc

3.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

3.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Milling is to be implemented for production of single material flours or blends used as foods or was raw materials/ ingredients for food products. Availability of quality raw materials and adequate drying are key in the production of quality flours. Milling operations used in FoodLAND relied on lab and pilot scale mills, mostly electric powered hammer mills. Operations of such mills requires minimal skills and these are largely available. The main innovation by FoodLAND includes the use of novel ingredients to develop formulations with nutritional, nutraceutical and functional properties superior to those of commercially available flours. These formulations have been tested and disseminated, with a view of facilitating commercialisation. The milling work on this project did not aim to determine the most appropriate milling processes but rather the utilisation of available processes. Hence the milling methods applied to different materials may not necessarily be the most efficient or economical.

3.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

Prerequisites for development and implementation of prototype are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Access to source of electricity (grid or generator)	M
2	Proximity to raw material sources	2
3	Appropriate raw material handling	1

4	Appropriate product packaging	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

3.6.3 Implementation

The implementation process for milling can be divided into the following key phases:

Phase 1: Planning and Preparation - 3 months

Milestones: Finalized production and operational plans.

Facility preparation and equipment procurement

Identify and acquire drying, milling, blending, and packaging (only if milled products are to be packaged and not further processed) equipment suitable for composite flour production.

Set up the production line and quality control mechanisms.

Phase 2: Pilot production and process optimization - 4 months

Milestones: Optimized production process and defined quality standards.

Raw material procurement and storage

Secure contracts with suppliers for raw materials.

Implement proper storage solutions to maintain raw material quality.

Pilot milling and associated further processing

Produce a small batches of flour and secondary products.

Analyze flours and flour products for nutritional, nutraceutical, functional and sensory properties.

Shelf stability assessment

Make process adjustments, if required.

Phase 3: Distribution and market entry preparation - 3 months

Objective: Develop the distribution network and prepare for product launch.

Key Tasks:

Establish partnerships with processors (if secondary processing is to be done by others), local retailers, community groups, and supermarkets for product distribution.

Train sales teams and distributors on the product's features, benefits, and proper handling.

Design and implement marketing campaigns to educate consumers on the product.

Develop educational content to raise awareness about the health benefits of the product, focusing on target groups (children, women, and families).

Milestone: Market readiness and distribution network setup

Phase 4: Commercial production 4 months

Objective: Transition from the prototype to large-scale production while maintaining product quality.

Key Tasks:

Finalize agreements with suppliers for sourcing of raw materials.

Set up production facilities for larger-scale drying, milling, and packaging (only for milled products to be packaged without further processing).

Finalize packaging designs, ensuring they are both cost-effective and appealing to consumers.

Determine products properties and use results to obtain certification.

Produce at commercial scale

Milestone: Successful Scaling of Production

Phase 5: Commercial launch and monitoring - 3 months

Objective: Officially launch the products into the market and monitor its performance.

Tasks:

Initiate the product launch, making it available in retail outlets and online stores.

Monitor sales and consumer feedback to assess the initial reception and identify any improvements.

Collect data on customer satisfaction, adoption rates, and overall demand.

Milestone: Official product launch and availability on market

3.6.4 Management

Management of the prototype will entail the following:

Value chain linkages establishment: Linkages with raw materials suppliers are to be established to facilitate raw materials acquisition. Linkages with processors to undertake further processing of flours are also required.

Quality assurance: To include raw materials testing to establish conformity to quality standards; process control and regular quality assessment.

Equipment and facilities maintenance: Equipment and facilities used for milling operations should be maintained in good conditions. Equipment should be serviced regularly, according to manufacturer's guidelines and best practices for the equipment maintenance.

3.7 Conclusions

Milling operations are required to feed into most of the ingredients and food products produced reported on in D 5.11 and D 5.14. The quality of the ingredients and food products is therefore dependent on the processes used for milling. There is therefore need to ensure efficient connections between operators engaged in milling and other food actors.

4. Fish smoking (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)

4.1 Protocol background, motivation and objectives

Fish and fishery products represent valuable sources of nutrients and contribute to diversified and healthy diets (FAO, 2013). However, fresh fish is highly perishable, thus susceptible to post-harvest loss. At artisanal level smoking is one of the low cost preservation technologies available to processors. Smoking entails dehydration, imparts antioxidant and antibacterial properties from the phenolic compounds. Technically at artisanal level, it is for impartation of smoky flavour. Traditionally, fish is smoked using local kilns, mud and wattle, altona kiln,

mechanical, afos kiln and chokor kiln. However, the cited kilns expose fish to high levels of carcinogenic compounds (Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, PAH) from the dispersed phase of smoke, for example benzoαpyrine. NARO has developed a PAH safe smoking technology that gives a good quality smoked fish product with acceptable levels of PAH below 5 ppb.

The overall objective was to develop a prototype for producing safe, quality and stable preserved smoked fish products, thereby contributing to reducing fish post-harvest losses and economic returns to value-chain actors.

4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Live fish from three species, Nile tilapia, African catfish, and Barbus sp. were purchased from fish farmers in Kakiri, central Uganda. The fish was transported to the food processing plant at Food Biosciences and Agribusiness Research Program (FBA), National Agricultural Research Laboratories, Kawanda which is one of the NARO institutes with facilities for product development.

The smoked fish with acceptable levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) was prepared according to Masette *et al.*, (2018) using the NARO PAH-Safe Fish Smoking Kiln (Fig. 4.1).

Figure 4.1 NARO PAH-Safe Fish kiln

The processing steps are as follows; All the fish were drip dried for 1 hour in the sun and then placed on trays inside the smoking kiln. The different types of fish were placed into different chambers of the smoking kiln without cross contamination. Smoke was induced from matooke peelings and guava tree wood for a period of 3-4 hour at 40 °C (depending on the fat content of the fish species). This was gradually increased to 50 and 70 °C over a period of 4 hours. The kiln temperature was gradually increased to 100 °C for a period of 3 hours. This was maintained for a further 2 hours after the fish had been turned over so that the side that was up is directly facing the oven bottom. Then the heat source was removed and the fish allowed to cool to room temperature before packaging. The smoked products were put on stainless steel trays for inspection. Products were packaged in well ventilated waxed boxes and store at ambient temperature ready for market.

Figure 4.2. Smoking of fish using NARO PAH-safe fish smoking kiln

4.3 Summary of the outputs

4.3.1 Results and achievements

All the smoked fish samples had moisture content below the UNBS/EAS acceptable level of 15% for dried fish products. Water activity was maintained between 0.7 and 0.5 which is ideal for limiting mould growth. Smoked tilapia had

a TVC within the acceptable specification limit of 5 log cfu/g for the 8-week storage period. The smoked tilapia (6.9) remained sensorially acceptable throughout the storage period. Smoking was effective for shelf life extension of the fish especially tilapia for at least 8 weeks. It thus ensures long shelf life for fish.

4.3.2 Relevant production

Tinyiro S. E., Masette M., Akullo D., Wanda F. and Aruho C. Shelf-life assessment of improved primary processed Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) and African catfish (*Clarius gariepinus*) products. 3rd FAR4ViBE Scientific Conference, Arusha, Tanzania 29th – 31st October 2024.

4.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	PAH-safe smoking kiln	30 farmers/2 SMEs

4.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	PAH-safe smoking kiln	10% reduction in fresh fish post-harvest losses

4.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

4.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

The fabrication of the PAH-safe smoking kiln requires specialised engineering knowledge and practical skills. However, it has minimal maintenance requirements. Prerequisite programs especially good hygienic practices are important to have the best raw material prior to smoking. The smoking protocols are easy to follow and must be adhered to strictly. The kiln can be used at community level especially by women processor groups.

The limitation is a relatively high initial cost of the kiln. However, through group cooperative financing, this can be overcome.

4.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The prerequisites for development and implementation of the protocol are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Raw materials: Quality fresh fish handled well (Good Hygienic Practices) Nearby raw material source – lake, river, fish pond</i>	1
2	<i>Equipment: Well-constructed PAH-Safe smoking kiln</i>	1
3	<i>Energy: Biomass (firewood, charcoal)</i>	1
4	<i>Others: Potable water for washing</i>	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

4.6.3 Implementation

The implementation activities, milestones and estimated duration are provided below.

No.	Activity	Mile stones	Months					
			1	2	3	4	5	6

1	Baseline/Market survey (Knowledge about the market, user needs) and stakeholder mapping	Information on value chain actors/stakeholders and market requirements							
2	Procurement of raw materials, equipment, and other inputs from prequalified suppliers, fabrication of Kiln	Raw materials, equipment and other inputs in place							
3	Smoking of fish – testing and optimising conditions with fish processor groups (end-user setting) at pilot level	Smoking protocols and process conditions optimised Smoked fish products developed and profiled							
4	Market testing of smoked fish	Market test reports and customer feedback							
5	Scaling/Uptake of PAH-safe smoking technology at commercial scale	Private sector-led commercial production of smoked fish (At least 1 SME) UNBS certified smoked fish products on the market							

4.6.4 Management

The PAH-Safe smoking technology requires a well-constructed kiln. In addition implementers/users should adhere to established prerequisite programs (especially Good Hygienic Practices), SOPs, protocols and work flows. More so, a quality management system based on HACCP has to be put in place to ensure continuous production of quality and safe smoked fish products. Initial training of production staff on maintenance and operations of the PAH-safe smoking kiln is important for building local capacity. A program for continuous technical backstopping through scheduled monitoring visits by the technical team will help to keep operations on track.

4.7 Conclusions

The PAH-safe smoking technology was used to develop smoked fish products with extended shelf life. The technology can go a long way towards solving challenges of traditional smoking such as unhygienic kilns, exposure of fish to high levels of carcinogenic compounds (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, PAH). The technology will lead to nutritious and safe smoked fish products on the market which will improve health of consumers. In addition, market opportunities for regional and international trade in will be opened for processors as the smoked fish products meet quality standard requirements.

References

- Food and Agriculture Organization (2013). The State of Food and Agriculture. Food Systems for Better Nutrition. Rome. ISBN 978-92-5-107671-2. pp 114
- Masette M. (2013). Securing the nutritional value of freshwater fish products in the East, Central and Southern African region: Case study for Uganda. FAO Report
- Masette M., Candia, A., Yawe, J., Bwambale., M and D. Akullo (2018). Training Manual: Processing and preserving fish using PAH filter Smoking Kiln for improved safety and trade

5. Fish fermentation (Masaka/Kajjansi, UG)

5.1 Protocol background, motivation and objectives

Fish processing generates considerable amount of solid waste which is comprised of fins, frame, skin, head and viscera, contributing approximately 58% of the whole fish. Viscera alone account for 8% (Ogunja et al., 1990). These wastes are a potential environmental hazard, if not disposed of appropriately. More so, fish viscera are a potential source of macro and micronutrients which can be harnessed for development of fertiliser as well as animal feed. The main objective of this activity was to add value to fish offal by fermentation into silage for use as a base material for livestock and poultry feed.

4.2 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Solid fish hydrolysate feed was produced from fish offals/guts by lacto-fermentation (using lactic acid bacteria – LAB). A method similar to Arvanitoyannis and Kassaveti (2008), which is summarised in Figs 5.1 and 5.2, was used as described below; Wash the fish waste and containers to be used under running water. Weigh/determine the volume of the fish waste (5.25L). Comminute and blend the fish waste using a knife and blender/food processor respectively. Add clean/potable water (ordinary boiled water) to the homogenate in a ratio of 1:1 i.e. 1 part water to 1 part fish waste (5.25+5.25=10.5 L Total Volume). If using chlorinated water, leave the water to sit overnight to allow the chlorine to dissipate. Chlorine is an antimicrobial agent. Homogenize the mixture by agitation/stirring. Add lyophilized LAB at an inoculation rate of 0.02%. (2.1 g in 10500 mL). Add sugar at a rate of 8.5% of the total volume of mixture (892.5 g in 10500 mL). Stir the mixture to homogeneity. Transfer the mixture to the fermentation vessel (20 L jerry can). The vessel may be loosely capped however, an airlock should be used to cap the vessel and allow for anaerobic fermentation while containing the unpleasant odour from gases produced especially carbon dioxide (airlock was used). Fermentation proceeds at ambient temperature (25-30 °C) for 3-4 week. The fermentation is complete when a faint vinegar odor replaces the previous putrid odor. Enhance the carbohydrate/solids content of the fish hydrolysate by adding cassava flour/maize bran in a ratio of 1:1 (10 kg). Mix to homogeneity. Sun-dry the mixture on tarpaulin/black polythene sheet for approximately 48 hrs.

Figure 5.1 Preparation of fish hydrolysate by anaerobic fermentation of fish offals using lactic acid bacteria

Figure 5.2 Enhancement of carbohydrate/solids content and drying for ease of handling and extended storage of feed

5.3 Summary of the outputs

5.3.1 Results and achievements

The results of proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal are indicated in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal

Composition (% unless stated)	Feed from fermented fish offal	EAS 90 spec (compounded poultry feed)
Moisture content	16.19±1.52	13
Total Ash	5.31±0.18	
Crude Protein	13.62±2.02	14 – 22
Crude Fibre	3.47±0.65	7.5
Crude Fat	20.79±0.24	10 (max)
ME, Kcal/Kg	2264.14±78.16	2550 - 3000
Ca	0.41±0.16	1.0 – 4.5
P	0.71±0.25	0.7 – 1.0

The developed feed met the standard specification of a compounded poultry feed in terms of crude protein and phosphorus. Other attributes were marginally outside recommended range.

5.3.2 Relevant production

Masette M., Akullo D., Tinyiro S. E. and Aruho C (2023). Development of primary products from farmed fish. FoodLAND Annual meeting, Zanzibar, January 2023.

5.4 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Lacto-Fermentation of fish viscera/offal for animal feed	30 farmers/2 SMEs

5.5 Summary of the impacts

Key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system / tool / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Lacto-fermentation of fish viscera/offal for animal feed	At least 50% reduction in fish processing waste At least 20% increase in farmer income

5.6 Protocol for prototype implementation

5.6.1 Framework conditions for the prototype

Fermentation is a simple technology that is easy to implement and utilises readily available and low cost materials. The fermentation protocols are easy to follow and must be adhered to strictly. Fermentation can be done at community level

by fishers and processor groups targeting livestock farmers. The silage base material and dehydrated animal feed are easy to handle and store under ambient conditions.

5.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype / Technical architecture

The prerequisites for development and implementation of the protocol are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Raw materials: Quality fish offals from GHP (Good Hygienic Practices) processing, Proximity to raw material source – e.g. fish processing facility	1
2	Others: Potable water, knives, fermentation starter culture, sugar, blender, fermentation drum/jerrycan	1 - 2

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

5.6.3 Implementation

The implementation activities, milestones and estimated duration are provided below.

No.	Activity	Mile stones	Months							
			1	2	3	4	5	6		
1	Baseline/Market survey (Knowledge about the market, user needs) and stakeholder mapping – e.g. fish processors, animal feed producers	Information on value chain actors/stakeholders and market requirements								
2	Procurement of raw materials, equipment, and other inputs from prequalified suppliers,	Raw materials and other inputs in place								

3	Lacto-fermentation of fish offal – testing and optimising processes with fish processor groups (end-user setting) at pilot level	Salting protocols and process conditions optimised Salted fish products developed and profiled							
4	Market/on-farm testing of animal feed	Market/on-farm test reports and end-user feedback							
5	Scaling/Uptake of fermentation technology at commercial scale	Private sector-led commercial production of salted fish (At least 1 SME) UNBS certified animal feed products on the market							

5.6.4 Management

The technology for fermentation of fish offal to produce animal feed is technical but nonetheless manageable. Most of the required inputs are readily available at low cost. Implementers/users should adhere to established prerequisite programs especially good hygienic practices (GHPs), standard operating procedures (SOPs), protocols and work flows. More so, a quality management system based on HACCP should be put in place to ensure continuous production of quality and safe animal feed products. Initial training of production staff on the process is important for building local capacity and ensure sustainability. A program for continuous technical backstopping through scheduled monitoring visits by the technical team will help to keep operations on track.

5.7 Conclusions

The lacto-fermentation technology was used to develop animal feed products. The technology is inexpensive, uses locally available materials and is easy to implement by local SMEs. The product provides alternative protein, energy and micronutrient source for poultry farmers while mitigating the environmental impacts of fish processing wastes through adding value to them.

References

EAS (2023). EAS 90: Compounded poultry feed – Specification

Arvanitoyannis, I. S., & Kassaveti, A. (2008). Fish waste management: treatment methods and potential uses of treated waste. International Series. pp 861 – 924

Ogunja, J.C., Werimo, K.O. and Okemwa, E.N. (1990) A Case Study on High-Value Nile Perch Products. Proceedings of the Symposium on Post-Harvest Fish Technology, FAO, Cairo, Egypt.

<http://www.fao.org/docrep/005/t0606b/T0606B06.htm>

6. General conclusion

This deliverable describes primary processing equipment and procedures that have been developed for and applied to a variety of food materials. The described prototypes have been used to produce novel raw materials and ingredients that have been used in a wide diversity of food products. These prototypes are therefore critical elements of FoodLAND's aim of contributing to food and dietary diversification. The prototypes have been tested at lab scale and to a large extent validated in partnership with farmers and SMEs. Critical next steps include establishing of partnerships to facilitate commercialization the prototypes.

